

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

**Time trends in liver-related mortality in people with and without
diabetes: results from a population based study**

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Supplementary Table S1. Death rates, and 95% confidence intervals (CI), for liver-related causes in individuals with diabetes from 2010 to 2019, according to FSC MI.

	NVNA		Viral		Alcoholic	
	Death rate * 1,000 person-years	95%IC	Death rate * 1,000 person-years	95%IC	Death rate * 1,000 person-years	95%IC
2010	0.712	0.692-0.731	0.297	0.276-0.317	0.114	0.107-0.122
2011	0.653	0.630-0.676	0.301	0.284-0.319	0.106	0.099-0.112
2012	0.569	0.552-0.585	0.293	0.281-0.306	0.129	0.120-0.139
2013	0.480	0.470-0.491	0.253	0.238-0.270	0.062	0.056-0.068
2014	0.534	0.524-0.544	0.208	0.199-0.218	0.084	0.076-0.091
2015	0.470	0.453-0.486	0.267	0.253-0.281	0.086	0.079-0.093
2016	0.429	0.407-0.451	0.229	0.215-0.244	0.062	0.050-0.073
2017	0.465	0.443-0.486	0.243	0.225-0.262	0.054	0.046-0.063
2018	0.506	0.479-0.533	0.170	0.155-0.185	0.051	0.044-0.058
2019	0.445	0.416-0.474	0.150	0.132-0.168	0.067	0.053-0.080

Supplementary Table S2. Proportionate mortality, and 95% confidence intervals (CI), for liver-related causes in individuals with diabetes from 2010 to 2019, according to FSC MI.

	NVNA		Viral		Alcoholic	
	Proportionate mortality	95%IC	Proportionate mortality	95%IC	Proportionate mortality	95%IC
2010	63%	59%-68%	26%	22%-30%	10%	7%-13%
2011	62%	57%-66%	29%	24%-33%	10%	7%-13%
2012	57%	53%-62%	30%	26%-34%	13%	10%-16%
2013	60%	56%-65%	32%	27%-36%	8%	5%-10%
2014	65%	60%-69%	25%	21%-29%	10%	7%-13%
2015	57%	52%-62%	32%	28%-37%	11%	8%-14%
2016	59%	54%-64%	32%	27%-36%	9%	6%-12%
2017	61%	56%-66%	32%	27%-37%	7%	5%-10%
2018	70%	65%-74%	23%	19%-28%	7%	5%-10%
2019	67%	62%-72%	23%	18%-27%	10%	7%-13%

Supplementary Table S3. Death rates, and 95% confidence intervals (CI), for liver-related causes in individuals without diabetes from 2010 to 2019, according to FSC MI.

	NVNA		Viral		Alcoholic	
	Death rate * 1,000 person-years	95%IC	Death rate * 1,000 person-years	95%IC	Death rate * 1,000 person-years	95%IC
2010	0.200	0.184-0.217	0.113	0.100-0.126	0.063	0.042-0.083
2011	0.215	0.206-0.224	0.077	0.072-0.083	0.053	0.049-0.057
2012	0.193	0.185-0.202	0.103	0.090-0.111	0.053	0.047-0.060
2013	0.180	0.172-0.188	0.098	0.092-0.104	0.035	0.031-0.039
2014	0.180	0.173-0.187	0.105	0.098-0.111	0.050	0.046-0.055
2015	0.189	0.178-0.199	0.099	0.091-0.108	0.020	0.019-0.022
2016	0.168	0.151-0.184	0.100	0.090-0.109	0.040	0.033-0.047
2017	0.146	0.122-0.169	0.085	0.078-0.092	0.031	0.025-0.037
2018	0.134	0.125-0.143	0.047	0.035-0.059	0.021	0.014-0.028
2019	0.133	0.115-0.151	0.086	0.069-0.102	0.036	0.027-0.046

Supplementary Table S4. Proportionate mortality, and 95% confidence intervals (CI), for liver-related causes in individuals without diabetes from 2010 to 2019, according to FSC MI.

	NVNA		Viral		Alcoholic	
	Proportionate mortality	95%CI	Proportionate mortality	95%CI	Proportionate mortality	95%CI
2010	53%	45%-61%	30%	23%-37%	17%	9%-24%
2011	63%	57%-68%	24%	19%-29%	13%	9%-18%
2012	56%	51%-61%	28%	24%-33%	16%	12%-20%
2013	57%	53%-62%	31%	27%-35%	11%	9%-14%
2014	58%	54%-62%	30%	26%-33%	12%	9%-15%
2015	57%	53%-61%	34%	30%-37%	9%	7%-12%
2016	55%	51%-59%	33%	30%-37%	11%	9%-14%
2017	54%	49%-59%	34%	30%-38%	12%	9%-15%
2018	61%	56%-65%	29%	25%-33%	10%	8%-13%
2019	53%	49%-58%	33%	29%-39%	14%	11%-17%

Supplementary Table S5. Cause-specific death rates and standardized mortality ratios (SMRs), with their 95% confidence intervals (CI), in individuals with diabetes and without previous liver disease compared with controls in 2019.

	Individuals with diabetes	Individuals without diabetes	
Cause of death	Deaths * 1,000 person-years	Deaths * 1,000 person-years	SMR (95% CI)
Liver	0.47	0.26	1.80 (1.60-2.02)
NVNA	0.33	0.13	2.48 (2.14-2.83)
Viral	0.11	0.09	1.15 (0.88-1.46)
Alcoholic	0.03	0.04	0.96 (0.60-1.40)
Cardiovascular	13.21	8.28	1.58 (1.54-1.61)
Cancer	11.46	8.09	1.40 (1.36-1.43)

Supplementary Figure S1. Standardized mortality ratios (SMR) for liver, cardiovascular and cancer-related deaths among patients with diabetes compared with controls in 2019, according to FSC MI.

Supplementary Figure S2. Time trends in standardized mortality ratios (SMR) for cause-specific liver-related mortality in individuals with and without diabetes from 2010 to 2019, according to FCS MI.

Abbreviations: NVNA, non-alcoholic non-viral causes.